

THE ROOT OF ENVIRONMENTAL AND HISTORICAL TRAUMA OF COLONIZATION IN LITERATURE

S. Sivaranjini¹, M. S Joshia², I. Aadil³, S. Sharmila⁴, E. Rakshana Devi⁵

¹Assistant Professor

Annai Violet Arts and Science College

Chennai, Tamilnadu.

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Abstract: The goal of literary and environmental studies is to investigate both social commitments and methods. Following a similar path, eco-criticism begins with the belief that imagination and inquiry can strengthen, energize, and drive concern in order to significantly advance our understanding of environmental issues. This range of forms is consistent with other environmental humanities fields' perspectives on environmental phenomena, such as ethics, history, religious studies, and humanistic geography. A wide range of environmental issues must be addressed, with qualitative and quantitative reflections put on hold. Humankind's vision, will, and belief are the foundational discoveries and reinforced regimes. Take some time to appreciate nature's magic, which only manifests when humans adapt and remain committed to environmental restoration. Environment consists of all living and non living things which surround us as a supporting thing to survive the life better.

Keywords: Literature, Environment, human relationship with nature, colonization, fiction, climate.

I. INTRODUCTION

The basics of environmental studies are targeting materialistic lifestyle including science and technology. It is now universally realized that any future developmental activities have to be viewed in the light of its ultimate environmental impact. The tremendous industrial activity during the last few decades and the release of industrial wastes in to the environment, have been considered as disasters for next generation. Environmental pollutions such as named by deforestation, soil erosion, population explosion, global warming inference in ecosystem and biosphere are threatening the very existence of life on the earth. People are responsible for creating such conditions but wrongly ended up with unhealthy biosphere of this planet. The food chain is collapsed with such action as a result all animals, plants and their dependence cycle is disturbed. The support of good Insects, bacteria, virus and other organisms are failed to do their natural systematic sequences and destroyed by chemical wastes. Our planet is rich in biodiversity and holds this substance for millions of years. Like these species are strong in their tendency including intriguing, towering trees and other coral nets where all types of animals live together but modernity spoil their natural cycle. Since life is dependable upon the environment, its absence causes many adverse and harmful effects in recent decades. Many countries are facing the same problem of environmental pollutions and calamities. Without sustainable environment and natural resources, one cannot survive in this world. Our environment should be protected by us to gain clean drinking water, hygienic living conditions, clean and fresh air, fertile land, healthy food etc.

II. A STEP ON LITERATURE IN THE FIELD OF ENVIRONMENTAL STUDY

It is the investigation of the account of life and the connection between literature as well as the environment known as 'Eco-criticism' is the term the association between literature and the environment. Eco-criticism began primarily to deepen its origins during the time of early 1900s. This is visible that it has a very minimal line exists between literature and eco-criticism focused on the relationship between the individual and his surrounding environment. The term originated from ecology, which is the analysis of the various species and their natural environment, based on problems related to nature. Several novels, poetry, and other literary phenomena have portrayed the labeled term. It is demonstrated by multiple writers and artists including Ruskin Bond, Robert Frost, Anita Desai, Amitav Ghosh, and many more. This term has a unique place in literary criticism that has been explored internationally, including the study of humanity's approach to nature. Researching the perspectives of writers that have explored the connection between man and nature is a fascinating study.

The power of Nature is an immense query in several literary works in Literature. Colonialism has been a huge component of the global destruction of the environment. The powerful country had destroyed and conquered the essence of powerful materialistic things from nature. The world's social and cultural environment has drastically transformed in the hands of man and this approach and deconstruction are discussed in the literature. This Eco-criticism takes a huge step in texts and theories that investigate the bond between man and nature. As a result, Environmental studies have mastered significance in world literature in the name of colonialism, gender construction, tourism, tradition, and their impacts, etc. Several literary articles showed the motif of eco-study which was discussed by writers as an environmental concerned study. Some Indian articles were primarily discussed by Anita Desai, and Amitav Ghosh, so the majority tried to understand the journey of eco-criticism and study on the whole.

In Anita Desai's *Cry, the Peacock* (1963), the relationship between nature and man is essential and vital. In this novel, the undiscovered female psychology is investigated by natural imagery moreover the symbolism of nature is examined through Maya's internal mind and unfolded her deformed world. In general, the writer is always used nature as a tool to expose the emotions of a human being. In *Hungry Tide* (2005), Amitav shares the background of the Sundarbans continuously exploring the struggle between nature and man and represents the tensions between the people and the water, and the wildlife of the area. In *Love in the Time of Cholera* Gabriel explained the story of almost 60 years, during which Columbia experienced civil wars, environmental destruction, and rampant cholera outbreaks. The novel has a lot of details to say about the moral corruption of society, and the way how humans are driven by greed can lead to destroying the environment around them.

III. HISTORICAL TRAUMA OF COLONIZATION

Colonization always affects nature and people. Around the world today, inflexible conflict is found in many regions that were once colonized or controlled by Western European or Soviet powers. The source of many of these extended conflicts, in large part of the privileging formation of non-democratic or non-participatory governmental systems. The long-term habitation of colonization is still applied in space too. Space is colonized by international countries and they have their station for their research. Humans haven't even attempted to live in Antarctica or under Earth's seas, or underground space of Earth. These ideas are spoilers and dangerous to the human species. In the same way, the idea of colonizing space is a complete disaster for human beings. Any kind of colonialism implies the domination of people's life and culture. The main goal of colonialism is to build their root in someone else territory or build colonies. As a result, they take the order to control the life of natives in political, economic, cultural, environmental, and social spheres. Every colonization method has the stage of inventing disasters in one way. These disasters can be divided into two types; human disasters and natural disasters. These two affect the natural cycle of breathing on Earth. Industrialization is the core concept of occupying lands and provides materialistic life. The development is only accepted when it never touched the life source of nature.

IV. CLIMATE CRISIS

New novels and poetry mostly focused on climate change known as climate fiction, or cli-fi works, and published all the seasons. Fiction allows us to imagine possible futures, good and also bad predictions. The climate crisis may be unprecedented, but there are a few key ways in which past literature portrays an important perspective on the bias of the present crisis. Literary works such as Byron's *Darkness*, Percy Shelley's *Mont Blanc*, and Mary Shelley's *Frankenstein* expose unlimited anxieties about human vulnerability to the environment that completely changed even as they deal with

our influence to control the environment. Even the oldest epic poem, The Epic of Gilgamesh (1800 BC), secured the concept of climate change. The huge flood like the story of Noah in the Old Testament is mentioned there. Now, the sea level is increased by climate change which makes us think deeper about the concept. These historical climatic shifts were not considered man-made mistakes but it is questionable after industrialization. People have accused climate change of happening only because of industrialization and accepted it as a man-made mistake. One of the ironies of modernity is that the development of the global climate as an object of study, it seems that takes apart from human life, concurs with the growth of carbon capitalism. Adeline Johns-Putra says that Climate change is inadequate now, for we are in a “climate emergency.” The climate emergency insists we consider our responsibilities on a global range rather than as individuals and people should take action against their committed mistakes which already affect nature. This is where literature generally approaches us. It gives us the headspace in which to presume through these difficult questions. All over the world, people have to make major changes to their lifestyles, to avoid climate change. People should understand that they are the living saviors to protect their land. From Noah’s Ark to Tsunami, history always repeats the laziness and immaturity of people and their irresponsible behavior to secure nature. Here is the data released by BBC and it is the current status for increasing the level of carbon dioxide with the list of global countries.

The world's top emitters of carbon dioxide

Megatonnes of CO2 per year

Note: One megatonne = 1,000,000 tonnes

This is one data but the list is so vast because the area of damage rate is too high for example the count of animals, deforestation, wildfire, sea level, co2 emissions, soil and water damages, and so on. Several studies have evidence that literature has the social responsibility to shape young minds.

V. LANDS AND MASTERMINDS

Land resources are one of the most important natural wealth of the country. The utilization of the land according to its use capability leads to the best growth. The innocent people failed to secure their lands. As a result, agricultural lands turned into industrial land. The landlords are the masters and control the regional area under the guidance of powerful people. Tribal people have been the most marginalized, isolated, and deprived population of any land. They have zero knowledge of protecting and securing their land. The Sentinelese are living on North Sentinel Island and the Andaman Islands in the Indian Ocean. They vigorously reject all contact with outsiders. They are the most isolated tribes in the world. They use their hand-made weapons to protect nature from us or else those islands are easily occupied by landlords.

The basic charts of identifying the types of disasters given below:

VI. MULTI-GENRES OF ENVIRONMENTAL LITERATURE

- **ENVIRONMENTAL ACTIVISM:**

- Carson, Rachel. *Silent Spring*. 1962.
- Leopold, Aldo. *A Sand County Almanac*. 1949.
- Haynes, Diane. *Flight or Fight*. 2006.
- Kingsolver, Barbara. *Animal, Vegetable, Miracle: a Year of Food Life*. 2007.
- Schwartz, Dan. *No Cure for Nature*. 2009

- **ENVIRONMENTAL FICTION:**

- Dulemba, Elizabeth. *A Bird on Water Street*. 2014.
- Kingsolver, Barbara. *Prodigal Summer*. 2000.
- Kingsolver, Barbara. *Flight Behavior*. 2012

- **NATURE WRITING:**

- Dillard, Annie. *Pilgrim at Tinker Creek*. 1975.
- Thoreau, Henry David. *Walden*. 1854.
- Muir, John. *My First Summer in the Sierra*. 1911.

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These works and studies generally deal with humanity's impact on nature, whereas eco-fiction is more about interaction with the environment, including the developments and consequences. This is the concept of categorizing stories as well as accompanying our natural world. The life lessons through stories are effective and informative for the younger generation. Through the work of Hyperobjects, people come to know that deep knowledge of a wide environmental situation, might allow us to take action toward a better future. The rhythm of Buddhism, science, nature, and culture, are examined in the mixture of a single vision.

VII. CONCLUSION

Modern education has been preventive itself to race, class, and gender which were the topics of the twentieth century. Nature is the source power of for worshipping, reproduction, and giving life support to all living and non-living creatures. Everything is changed when colonization exposed especially traitors are leveled up their trades and occupied the natural wealth and exported all the sources for money. At last, nature and powerless people suffer a lot and are treated as slaves. People are already experiencing loss of life and livelihood due to intensified storms, disasters, shortage of fresh water, the spread of disease, rising food prices, and the creation of climate refugees. The most devastating effects are visited on the poor, those with no involvement in creating the problem. A deep injustice is visible all over the territory of the independent land of occupation. As humanity persists to multiply, consume, and destroy, the environment will keep on being affected by our choices. The cause of industrialization and development might be forced people to select one choice without any option. Today, Literature can create awareness for people but success depends only on the hands of powerful people and the same power will act as a guard to protect nature.

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